

PARTICIPATIVE PROTOCOL MANUAL

Sub-task 2.1.2: Consumers deliberations

SUBMON with the support of EO will develop a Survey for the identification of general barriers to sustainable seafood acceptance by consumers. The survey will be sent to all actors previously identified in sub-task 2.1.1 and who accepted to support the Sea2See project. SUBMON will set up a team together with other partners to gather, categorise and analyse the results. With these initial results, four 1-day multi-stakeholder participative workshops to be held in Spain, Greece, Portugal and France to identify barriers to sustainable seafood consumption. All results obtained from the workshops will be gathered and analysed, and a matrix with the main barriers to overcome in each country ranked in terms of relevance and importance will be developed. A set of general proposals to overcome those barriers identified during the workshops will also be presented.

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What is Sea2See?

The Sea2see project will fill in existing seafood traceability gaps through development of an innovative end-to-end blockchain model and professional and consumer applications to increase trust and social acceptance of sustainably fished and farmed seafood. The project will provide technological solutions to answer the need of a valuable source of data collected throughout the whole seafood value chain, verified and covering inputs from diverse stakeholders. For that purpose, a specific focus will be put on active commitment of stakeholders and real empowerment of consumers through the implementation of societal and sectoral strategies for co-creation, communication and awareness raising. Under WP2, the main objective is to identify the knowledge gaps and respective difficulties of consumers to identify and consume sustainable seafood, while developing ways to overcome the barriers detected for their acceptance and involvement. WP2 will also trigger a transition towards more sustainable options for seafood consumption, both farmed and fished seafood, and will implement a comprehensive strategy on engaging consumers in taking more informed decisions.

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Consumer engagement in the seafood industry

Consumers have the right to know detailed information about the products they are purchasing, and they have the responsibility of checking available information for making informed decisions. These assumptions apply to all markets, and when it comes to the seafood industry, research has suggested that consumers have the potential to make a paradigm shift towards sustainable purchasing and consumption practices, when resources and tools are available to them.

Final consumers occupy a privileged position in the stakeholder map of the seafood value chain, as with their purchasing habits they drive revenues.

Analysing and understanding consumers' expectations, needs and purchasing trends is crucial to the feasibility of the entire seafood supply chain. In this regard, it is of utmost importance to listen to their needs and investigate information gaps, to plan strategic actions to overcome barriers to sustainable seafood consumption and product acceptance. In the last decades, consumers are increasingly asking for products transparency, claiming information on seafood traceability and sustainability before purchasing or consuming seafood.

Figure 1 – From awareness to behaviour change

Consumer engagement - Participation Protocol

This Participation Protocols Learning Manual was adapted from the original publication *Ocean Literacy Co-Creation Participation Protocol*, Devaney, M., Domegan, C., McHugh, P. B. Broome, M. Hogan and Piwowarczyk, J. (2015) *The Sea Change Participation Protocols Learning Manual*. EU Sea Change Project.

Given the similarities in terms of consultation objectives and dynamics, this protocol was thought to be a good fit for the Sea2See project.

What is the Participation Protocol?

Participation is about collaboration, empowerment and direct active engagement with your target group through ALL stages of the Sea2See work. Participation is about speaking and listening to people on their own terms. Participation goes significantly beyond just asking people for their opinions or what might be called 'participation by consultation'. It gives your target group a **voice** about the **barriers to change** and **ownership and responsibility for solutions** to influence their welfare. Research is interactive; it's 'with' and not 'on' your target group. As can be seen in Figure ii below, we are moving towards collaborating and empowering our target group.

Figure 2 – Levels of Participation ^{vii}

Why is the Participation Protocol Important?

One of the Sea2See overarching objectives is to seek a behaviour change in the way European citizens purchase and consume wild captured or farmed seafood. In order to do so, efforts will be put on closing **value-action gaps** to bring about a more seafood literate population. A value-action gap is a mismatch between a person's values/attitudes and behaviour or put another way, the difference between what people say and what people do. Direct active participation by individuals, communities and policy decision makers is the foundation for closing value-action gaps. Active participation to define the barriers to change and potential solutions is more empowering because it reflects **values** important to the individual and increases control. Participation provides the necessary dialogue, interaction and mutual learning to manage and "resolve highly complex issues"^{viii}, such as influencing human behaviour and the choices we make concerning our seafood consumption and our relationship with the ocean.

Attempts to influence behaviour should start with an understanding of the target group you want to do the changing. The activity is to work out **why they do what they do at present**, their values and motivations, and use this understanding to develop an offering that is equally appealing but with positive personal and/or social outcomes. Successful behaviour change is built through a **well-grounded understanding of current behaviour** and the people engaged in it.

Learning Objectives

This manual gives a brief introduction to the Sea2See Participation Protocol under WP2, and then outlines each of the participation tasks that must be completed by partners involved in Subtask 2.1.2. A number of worksheets and checklists are also provided in the tools section.

The manual was developed as a supporting tool to the Sea2See training sessions. By the end of this training partners should:

- ✓ Have a clear understanding of Participation Protocol
- ✓ Understand the difference between Participation Content, Context and Process
- ✓ Be familiar with the four Participation Consultation stages
- ✓ Have agreed on a trigger question to be used by all partners within the work package
- ✓ Understand how to use the ISM software
- ✓ Understand how to read Structural Maps
- ✓ Know who to include in the facilitation team
- ✓ Understand the golden rules of facilitation
- ✓ Understand the importance of choosing a suitable training venue
- ✓ Know about reporting requirements and
- ✓ Put in place a follow-up strategy with consultation participants.

TIMELINE OF THE CONSULTATION PROTOCOL

SUBTASKS	NOV22	DEC22	JAN23	FEB23	MAR23	APR23	MAY23	JUN23
1. Development of the survey	Active	Active	Light	Light	Light	Light	Light	Light
2. Revision and translation of the survey into native languages	Light	Light	Active	Active	Light	Light	Light	Light
3. Dissemination and collection of answers	Light	Light	Light	Active	Active	Active	Light	Light
4 Training sessions on Collective Intelligence method	Light	Light	Light	Active	Active	Light	Light	Light
5. Analysis and categorization of barriers within the internal working group in preparation to the participative workshop	Light	Light	Light	Light	Light	Active	Light	Light
6. 1-day multi-stakeholder workshops in France, Spain, Portugal and Greece	Light	Light	Light	Light	Light	Light	Active	Light
7. Deliverable D2.3 "Sea2See strategy on consumer-related stakeholders' engagement and sustainable seafood consumer acceptance increase	Light	Light	Light	Light	Light	Light	Active	Active

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Consultation Protocol

Partners will use a Collective Intelligence (CI) methodology to involve target group(s) in active, direct participation for the Sea2See project. CI is a **barriers** and **value structuring** methodology. CI is a process of **critical learning** and **reflection** followed by **action**, and then by more critical learning to enable mobilisation, design and development 'with' people rather than on their behalf. CI utilises easy to use software; Interpretive Structural Modelling (ISM), which aids participants in the consultation process. As can be seen below in Figure 1, CI takes participants through four stages: **Barrier Generation**, **Barrier Categorisation**, **Structuring Barriers** and **Generating Options** (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Collective Intelligence process

The first phase, **Barrier generation**, takes place mainly online, through an online survey and is complemented by activities during the one day consultation workshop. The second phase, **Barrier Categorisation**, is first done by an internal working group and then completed by participants during the one-day consultation workshop that will be organised in Portugal, France, Spain and Greece. The **Barrier Structuring** and the **Generating Options** phases are also completed by participants during the one day consultation workshop. The ISM software package is utilised during the Barrier Structuring phase: the group of participants answer a series of **relational questions** to determine which barriers are the most aggravating. The outcome is a structural map. The final stage of your consultation workshop is Generating Options. During this stage, the participants work in smaller groups. Each group is assigned a category(ies) and works together to generate **options to overcome the barriers** in their assigned category(ies). To complete your consultation process, a report of the barriers, a structural map together with solutions is sent to all participants (online and those who took part in the workshop).

Setting up for Your Consultation

A number of tasks must be completed before the first stage of Collective Intelligence and prior to your one day consultation workshop.

A) Establish an Internal Working Group

An **internal organisation based working group** consisting of 3 to 5 **members** must be created by each national team of partners to prepare the settings for your 1-day consultation workshop. The working group is best to include multidisciplinary profiles (eg.marine experts, social experts, seafood experts, scientific/academia etc.) to have different perspectives on the subject, and be able to have a fruitful conversation during the process.

Is advisable that the facilitator and co-facilitator of the workshop are partners of Sea2see WP2, and need to be impartial.

"And should there be a sudden loss of consciousness during this meeting, oxygen masks will drop from the ceiling."

A **strong facilitator** is required to manage the internal working group and its responsibilities; facilitate the consultations and play an impartial, neutral role in the 1-day multi-stakeholders workshop. Ideally, the facilitator must have attended the training. As a range of participants are included in the consultations, it is inevitable that they have a diverse range of interests, views, values and barriers, which may lead to conflict. The facilitator must be capable of **handling any conflict** and ensure your working group and consultation participants reach a unified approach.

Credits: Gary Rush, IAF CPF

A **co-facilitator** is present in the consultation workshop to aid the facilitator. The co-facilitator is responsible for recording the participant's views and inputting the data into the software package. The co-facilitator must be familiar with the CI process.

You are advised to have an **assistant** who is responsible for note taking or recording meetings and the consultation workshop. Important discussions take place during the course of the consultation workshop. It is helpful for these conversations to be captured and clarified by the assistant.

B) Consultation Software Package

A software package, Interpretive Structural Modelling, (ISM) was produced at NUI Galway as part of the EU Sea for Society project. The foundations of the software lie in systems thinking and in the works of John Warfield^{ix}. The software package identifies **relationships among barriers** and imposes structure on those barriers in order to **manage the complexity of the issue**. A detailed guide on how to use the ISM software is in **Appendix 1**. Use

Tool 2 to ensure you are familiar with the software prior to running your consultation workshop.

C) Prepare Materials for the Consultation Workshop

Prior to beginning your consultation workshop, ensure that you have ALL of the necessary materials in hand. A checklist of needed materials is in **Tool 3**.

D) Choosing a Consultation Workshop Venue

Choosing a suitable training venue for the consultation workshop is essential. The participants are spending an entire day in this room so it is important to ensure that the room is **spacious** and has **natural daylight**. The room must have lots of **clear wall space** to display the A4 sheets with barriers, categories and options written on them. If there is no wall space OR you cannot stick A4 sheets on the walls, you will need a large number of poster boards. At the beginning of the session the room must be set-up in a **U-shape style**. Later on in the workshop, participants will be broken into smaller groups so it must be possible to **reconfigure the room** at this point. When choosing a training venue, use the checklist in **Tool 4** to ensure that it meets all of the criteria. An example of an excellent workshop venue can be seen below in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Consultation Venue

E) Participant Consultation Recruitment (our target audience for the online survey and the workshop)

The following list of stakeholders groups defines the target of our online survey. These stakeholders are at the final part of the seafood value chain.

Consumers' Identification

- 1.1. Individuals & segments (definition of the people who we want to address our actions eg. Families, Household, citizens, WTP, millennials)
- 1.2. Public Administration & Institutions
- 1.3. Consumer clusters (groups of consumers, eco-consumption groups, local associations)
- 1.4. Supermarkets (small, medium, big size)
- 1.5. Public markets (e.g. fish auction, local markets, Fishmongers)
- 1.6. HORECA
 - 1.6.1. Hotels

- 1.6.2. Restaurantes (chefs)
- 1.6.3. Catering
- 1.7. Social services and municipalities (eg. public places where food is offered for low income citizens)
- 1.8. Canteens (eg. schools, universities, public administration, private companies, etc)
- 1.9. Cooking Schools
- 1.10. Knowledge Brokers
- 1.11. Consultancy and advocacy organisations or individuals
- 1.12. NGOs
- 1.13. Twin project & similars initiatives
- 1.14. Networks (Eg. COST)
- 1.15. Media
 - 1.15.1. Local & National press agencies
 - 1.15.2. TV & Radio Shows (podcasts)
- 1.16. Food & Sustainability Influencers
 - 1.16.1. Seafood ambassadors
 - 1.16.2. Food Influencers
 - 1.16.3. Food writers

However, to ensure a profitable 1-day multi-stakeholders workshop, it is important to select a few relevant stakeholders profiles that could also be part of other levels of the seafood value chain. We suggest referring to D1.1 for a comprehensive list of stakeholders for the Sea2See project.

It is preferable to select participants that come from different sectors (e.g. administration, academia, HORECA, seafood production, representative of consumer segments, seafood value chain experts, marketing experts, consultants etc.). We encourage select stakeholders to ensure gender balance.

For the consultation workshop, you must select a minimum of **15 participants** and a maximum of **21 participants**. For the participants you want to invite to the one-day consultation, you are asking them to commit to a full **one-day consultation** and some **online work** prior to the consultation. If your invited participant cannot commit to this, they can still be included in the Barrier Generation task that takes place online, through the survey.

QUICK TIPS

Clearly communicate the benefits of participating in the consultation workshop:

- A wonderful opportunity to share their opinions regarding barriers to Sustainable Seafood consumption.
- The opportunity to network with other powerful stakeholders.
- The opportunity to learn about the valuable methodology being used by Sea2see, and the potential to use this methodology in their own work.
- The local facilitators will remain open to helping participants if they wish to use the CI methodology.

F) In-House Dry Run

Prior to running your workshop, it is strongly advised that you first run an internal workshop to ensure you are familiar with all aspects of CI and the ISM software.

THE COLLECTIVE INTELLIGENCE PROCESS

PART 1

Online Consultation and preparatory activities of the internal working group

Task 1 – online Barrier Generation

The questionnaire is developed by SUBMON, in collaboration with Ethic Ocean. The main objective of the survey is to identify and explore general barriers to sustainable seafood consumption and acceptance. The information gathered with this survey will be the baseline for the 1-day multi-stakeholders participative workshops that will take place in Spain, France, Greece, and Portugal as part of the Collective Intelligence methodology.

The questionnaire consists of 4 sections:

- **Section 1** aims to profile purchasing/consumption habits from respondents and collect data on the knowledge and awareness of seafood consumption.
- **Section 2** (the most important) is to gather barriers.

- **Section 3** is to gather demographic information of respondents.
- **Section 4** explores future engagement in the Sea2See project.

To facilitate the collection of barriers in section 2, some examples of starter phrases have been provided:

Sample starter phrases for Barrier Generation

Failure to...	Others...
Lack of...	Inability to...
Hostility toward...	Refusal to...
Shortage of...	Conflict between...
Inadequate...	Unwillingness to...
Interference from...	Demand for..
	Resistance...

The EU Survey tool, an online survey-management system offered by the European Commission, is used to create the survey. The questionnaire will take approximately 5 minutes to complete.

Barrier Categorization

Internal working group
session to categorize
barriers collected

2

Task 2 – Collation and Categorization of Barriers during the internal working group session

Once the survey has closed, the internal working group collate ALL of the barriers received and transcribe them to a word document. The working group **deletes any duplicate barriers**. Duplicate barriers are barriers that are an exact copy of a previously identified barrier. The working group must take care to only delete barriers that are **obvious duplicates**. Each barrier statement should only contain one idea. If the barrier contains more than one idea, the internal working group split the barrier into two separate barriers.

A Word of Caution!

You need to keep track of what duplicate barriers you deleted and why as well as the barriers divided into 2 barriers.

EXAMPLE 1 (Taken from SeaChange project)

Experiential education is not institutionally promoted and there is a lack of a systemic approach to the system of teaching curricular competences. → split into 2 barrier statements

EXAMPLE 2 (Taken from SeaChange project)

The sea is considered as an unlimited resource to be used.

We think that the ocean is unalterable

Merged into 1 barrier statement: The ocean is considered an unlimited an unalterable resource to be used

EXAMPLE 3 (Taken from SeaChange project)

Only the surface level of the ocean is known by the general public

The internal processes of the ocean are unknown and it is difficult to bring them closer to the society

Merged into 1 barrier statement: The ocean is poorly known, the general public knows it superficially. The internal processes are unknown and it is difficult to bring society closer to these issues.

Task 3 – First Stage Barrier Categorisation within the internal working group

1. Set up the boards for barriers organization

When all the barriers have been transcribed to A4 sheets, the members of the working group place **10 white A4 sheets** (landscape) on a separate wall/display board, ordered horizontally from left to right across the wall as high as you can reach. Leave space between the ten white pages so that you can have two columns of barriers beneath.

2. Organizing barriers in categories using the commonality criteria

Select any **8 barriers at random** from the pool of barriers and move them beneath the first 8 white A4 sheets, leaving the last two white sheets empty. The working group must ensure that the eight barriers on the wall are **distinct barriers**. Take a **9th barrier** at random from the barrier pile. The group engages in **paired comparison** between barrier 9 and **each** of the 8 barriers on the wall/display board. For each of the 8 paired comparisons, the facilitator asks the internal working group the following question:

Do you see any commonality between this barrier and this one on the wall?

The facilitator does this for each of the 8 barriers in turn. The facilitator also asks the group:

“With which item does the barrier have the strongest commonality?”

If a barrier does not have a strong commonality with any of the 8 categories, place it beneath one of the two remaining empty categories (9th and 10th white A4 sheets). Repeat the steps above for barriers 10, 11, 12, etc. Continue until there are four or more barriers in at least five categories (minimum of 20 barriers on your wall broken down into 5+ categories).

3. Naming the barrier categories

When there are **four or more barriers** in a category set, the working group gives a name to the category. Make sure there is agreement on a category name. If a category name does not come easily to the group at this stage, leave the naming of the category until later in the

process. Repeat the above until at least five of the categories have names.

The Internal working group continues this process until all barriers are categorised.

There must be at least four barriers within each category. If there is a category with less than four barriers, try to place these barriers within another category.

4. Finalization

The working group **reviews the categories** and ensures everyone is happy with the categorisation. Remove barriers from the wall/display board, category by category. Keep these barriers and category names safe as they will be reused for the consultation workshop. The team should transcribe all of the categories and barriers within each category to a word document. Send the list of categories and barriers to the 15-21 workshop participants prior to the 1-day multi stakeholder workshop, to give them time to familiarise themselves with the topics.

5. Transcription

The internal working group also has to **transcribe** all barrier statements to blue A4 sheets, one barrier per sheet, in preparation for the consultation workshop. When transcribing the barriers onto the A4 sheets, each barrier is numbered, the number given should correspond to the number that the barrier has in the ISM software. (See **Appendix 1** for more information on the ISM software)

Figure 3 – Barrier Categorisation

PART 2

1-day multi-stakeholders Consultation Workshop

At this point, you are now set up to run your consultation workshop. The facilitator and co-facilitator conduct the consultation workshop with recruited participants. Remember to set up your room - all of the categories/barriers will need to be on display in your workshop before participants arrive.

Task 4 – Introduction to Workshop

The workshop itself starts with the facilitator welcoming participants and describing the broad goals of the session:

- To **work together** to understand **barriers**
- To **work together** to **generate options to overcome barriers**

Taking turns, participants introduce themselves; provide their name, the organisation they represent and their connection with the project. Depending on the group and the cultural context, there may be a need for an **ice-breaker exercise**.

As part of your introduction to the consultation workshop, it's helpful for all to distinguish Context, Content and Processes of the workshop.

Context: Remind participants that you are working in a particular context defined by the Sea2see project.

Content: Remind participants that their primary role is to **review barriers, structure them and generate options relevant to the context** and the particular issue they are addressing.

Process: Remind participants that the facilitation team is there to **manage the flow of activities**, including the implementation of various methodologies that will allow us to accomplish our goals. Remember, facilitators are **not there to influence the content**.

A suggested timeline for the consultation one day workshop is outlined in **Appendix 4**.

Task 5 – Collective Barrier Generation (2nd stage)

There is a second stage of Barrier Generation. It involves the 15-21 participants who will be attending the one-day consultation workshop. These workshop participants, contacted via e-mail before the workshop, are presented with a **complete list of the barriers generated by all online participants**. There is no need to send the clarifications at this stage. The workshop participants are asked to take some time to familiarise themselves with the barriers. On review of the complete list of barriers, the participants may **generate additional barriers**.

Task 6 – Collation and categorization of Barriers (2nd stage)

The facilitator invites and guides the participants through the barrier categories and allows them some time to refresh their memories and **review the barriers and categories**. As the categories have been emailed to the participants prior to the workshop, the participants should be relatively familiar with the categories and barriers.

Following the review of the categories, you ask participants if they are happy with the barrier categorisation. If the participants feel that some barriers would be more appropriate in another category, they are given the opportunity to move them. **Green sticky notes** are made available to the participants who wish to move barriers to another category. You instruct participants to take one sticky note, write their name on it and place it on one of the barriers on the wall/display board that they think would be **more appropriate in another category**. You then review and discuss the proposed category amendments with the group and make any necessary modifications, removing the green sticky notes as you go. At this stage, the participants should also be encouraged to ask for the rationale for the re-categorisation of individual barriers.

Figure 4 – Second Stage Barrier Categorisation

The internal working group adds any extra barriers generated by the workshop participants and again

deletes any duplicate barriers or divides barriers that contain more than one idea into two separate barriers.

This completed list of barriers from the two rounds of barrier generation (online + collective during the workshop) is then inputted into the ISM software. Most of the work could be done prior to the workshop, any edit/changes derived from the workshop discussion could be applied. Details on how to do this can be found in the **ISM software guide** in **Appendix 1**. The internal working group also has to **transcribe** all barrier statements to blue A4 sheets, one barrier per sheet, in preparation for the consultation workshop. When transcribing the barriers onto the A4 sheets, each barrier is numbered, the number given should correspond to the number that the barrier has in the ISM software.

Task 7 – Voting for Most Important Barriers

Now engage the group in a voting process to identify the most important barriers:

- Distribute a set of **red sticky dots** to participants. The number of red sticky dots given to participants varies depending on how many barrier categories there are. If there are 8 categories, distribute a set of 8 red sticky dots, if there are 9 categories, distribute a set of 9 red sticky dots, etc. Participants are asked to place one red sticky dot on one barrier from each category they **consider to be the most important**.
- Distribute to participants **4 additional red sticky dots** (the number of additional sticky dots remains the same whether there are 8, 10 or 12 barrier categories). Ask participants to place the sticky dots on any four remaining barriers they consider to be of **high importance from any category**. The additional red sticky dots can be placed on a barrier that the participant has previously voted for if they consider it to be very important.
- Based on collective selections of the group, identify the top 10, 11 or 12 barriers for structuring. If there is a tie between barriers, the facilitator may include more or less barriers (between 11 and 13 barriers is the ideal number) in the structuring.

Figure 5 – Voting for the Most Important Barriers

Task 8 – Enter Barriers into the ISM software (structuring barriers)

A coffee break for participants at this point allows the co-facilitator to move the top voted barriers into the **structuring field** in the ISM software (revisit the ISM software guide in **Appendix 1**). Activate the structuring software tab and enter the relational statement **significantly aggravates** in the keyword cell. Check to see that the context statement is visible in the structuring tab. A relational question will be identified; the software package will then generate questions which will be projected onto a screen in front of the group. (The software will generate questions in English, and the facilitator will translate them to the participants).

Task 9 – Barrier Group Structuring

Your relational question for barrier structuring is **“Does barrier A significantly aggravate barrier B?”** When the first relational question appears on the screen read the question **slowly** to participants. Read with curiosity, interest, correct emphasis, but without prejudice. After participants have had time to consider the question, ask a simple question such as: **“What do you think?”**, or **“Does anyone see a relationship between these two barriers?”** When a participant presents an argument in favour of a yes vote (i.e., that one element significantly aggravates another), the facilitator may ask them to **clarify their reasoning for the group**, using questions such as: **“Can you explain your thinking to the group?”**, or **“Can you elaborate and share your rationale with the group?”** When asking these questions in your own local context, use phrasing that is most culturally appropriate. Maintain a stance of curiosity, reflectiveness and neutrality.

EXAMPLE 1

Barrier A: Lack of informative material in supermarket

Barrier B: Lack of labelling in seafood product

Does Barrier A significantly aggravate Barrier B? YES

Figure 6 – Structuring Barriers

Keep in mind that for participants this is a **new process** and so it's important to take care when presenting relational questions. Also, it's important to note to participants that this is not a debate: it's **not about winning an argument**; it's not about right or wrong answers. It's about being **reflective, curious, open**, and **providing rationales** for what you think.

When a participant presents an argument in favor of a no vote (i.e., that one element does not significantly aggravate another), the facilitator may ask them to clarify their reasoning for the group, using questions such as: "Can you explain your thinking to the group?" Again, maintain a stance of curiosity, reflectiveness and neutrality. After one person has spoken and presented their rationale, ask the question: "**What do other people think?**", or "**Are there other thoughts or opinions?**" After the group has finished deliberating, take a vote using a show of hands, asking the question "How many say 'yes' (i.e., Element A does significantly aggravate element B). If at least 60% vote yes (For example, if 12 of your 20 participants say 'yes'), click the 'yes' button in the software. If it's less than 60% enter no. (Adapt the % to the number of participants in your workshop)

For the first 10 comparisons and votes, it is important to **maintain a slow deliberative pace** as above. As workshop participants become more familiar with the process it may be possible to move faster. There may be some relational questions that are immediately clear to the entire group and don't require very much discussion. Every time a barrier appears for the first time, it is important to take a moment to **review the meaning of the barrier with the group**.

The group will get tired and fatigued, so you need to keep them engaged throughout and perhaps **include several short breaks**. When structuring 12 barriers, there will be 50 – 70 decisions that need to be made by the group, so pace yourself and time breaks appropriately. When all barriers are structured, the software will tell you that structuring is complete and your structural map is now ready.

A Word of Caution

Be sure to save your structural map and the ISM file at this point.

Key Principles to Keep in Mind When Structuring

- Remind participants that it's not about being right or wrong; it's about being curious, reflective and open.
- It is a new process for most participants so take your time. Read relational questions slowly with curiosity and interest. Do not judge the participants.
- Allow for unscheduled breaks if the group becomes fatigued.

Task 10 - Review the Structural Map

Display the structural map provided by the software on the screen and explain to workshop participants how to interpret the structure. **The structural map is read from left to right, with barriers on the left having the most aggravation.** There may be **multiple paths of aggravation** that need to be described, depending on how complex the structure is. Some barriers may be in **cycles** i.e., with two or more barriers appearing together in a box, which means that these barriers are reciprocally inter-related.

The participants generally find the structural map interesting and engage in **animated discussion** of the results. However, they may, as a whole, want to **revisit the placement of one or two barriers**, even though it reflects their original voting. In this situation, barriers can be removed and restructured. This process of restructuring a barrier can sometimes **facilitate deeper learning** in relation to particular barriers (details on restructuring can be found in the ISM Software Guide).

A selection of structural maps from the Sea for Society stakeholder consultations can be seen below in Figures 7, 8 and 9.

Figure 7 – Sea for Society, Irish Food Supply Stakeholder Map

Figure 8 – Sea for Society, Swedish Energy Stakeholder Map

Figure 9 – Sea for Society, Italian Energy Stakeholder Map

The workshop participants break for refreshments after structuring barriers and before generating options. The facilitators may need to move the categories and related barriers around the wall/display boards to ensure that the participants will have sufficient space to post the options they are about to generate. Recall, the layout of the room alters from a U-shape to smaller group tables in a circular arrangement now.

Task 11 – Generate and Discuss Options

We recommend keeping this final phase as light as possible. Keep in mind that there will be a hackathon dedicated to generating solutions to the barriers identified.

Participants are divided into **four smaller groups**, each tackling two of the eight categories (the number of groups will depend on the number of categories that were generated). During the first round of options generation, participants are asked to focus on their first assigned barrier category. Participants, in their smaller groups, are asked to generate options in response to the barriers in the given category. The facilitator uses “**What are options for overcoming the barriers in the category___?**” as guiding question for the options stage. Options may include, for example, **Initiatives, Programmes, Actions, Recommendations, Policies, Activities**, etc. A handout to guide option generation can be distributed to participants during the Generating Options stage (**Appendix 5**). The smaller participant groups record all their options on a sheet of paper.

Continue this exchange process until all options have been generated and discussed within their smaller group. Participants transcribe all options onto **pink A4 paper**, one option per page, written in large font with markers, and post their options on the wall beneath the appropriate category heading.

The facilitator invites participants to repeat task 1 above for the second assigned barrier category

Task 12 – Present and Selection of Options

Each group **nominates one person** to present the options the smaller group proposed to all workshop participants. Other participants have **an opportunity to ask questions** for clarification.

Figure 10 – Presentation of Options

Distribute to all workshop participants a set of **red sticky dots** (one per category). For each of the sticky dots, participants place it on one option from each of the categories (if there are 9 categories, the participants are given 9 sticky dots, if there are 10 categories, participants get 10 sticky dots etc.). Participants are asked to select options based on the following criteria that

- Will have a
- **high impact.**
- The option is
- **feasible.**
Can be rolled out in a **reasonable time-frame.** There are people who could **champion** the option.

Distribute to all participants **4 additional red sticky dots.** Ask participants to place the sticky dots on any four options they consider to be of **high importance** from any category. Participants can use these 4 red sticky dots to vote for options they have already voted for if they consider the option to be very important. Based on collective selections of the group, **identify the top ranked options** by counting how votes each option has received. Review and discuss selected options with participants.

Wrap-Up and Follow-Up

The consultation workshop is now coming to an end. The facilitator and co-facilitator thank all participants for their time and contributions to Sea Change. Remind the participants that a **report of the consultation** will be sent to them, along with a **final project report** and other materials, if they wish. The facilitator must ensure they have all the participants' e-mail/addresses for follow-up as well as storing all the barriers, categories and options for reporting.

Task 12 – Prepare a Summary Report

Each partner is required to submit a summary report following each consultation. The report includes all barriers generated, as well as their clarifications, the categories that were generated, the structural map and the options generated by the workshop participants. A sample report will be sent to all partners following the training. Partners should use this report as a **template** when completing their own reports.

In order to write the report the facilitation team must take all of the barriers, options and categories from the wall. Each category should be placed into a separate folder with the category heading, followed by all of the barriers within that category and all of the options. The facilitation team is also advised to take photos of the categories, barriers and options before taking them down from the wall.

Task 13 – Event Debrief

Following each consultation the facilitation team should take some time to reflect on the consultation. **Tool 4** can be used to identify **what worked well**, **what didn't work well** and **what you would do differently** if you were doing it again.

TOOLS

Tool 1 – ISM Software Checklist

How and Why: Use this checklist to ensure you are familiar with the ISM software package.

Enter Workshop Information	
Enter Participants Information	
Enter Facilitator Information	
Enter Barriers	
Enter Clarifications	
Move barriers into the Structuring Tab	
Enter Keyword and Context Statement in Structuring Tab	
Structuring	
Restructuring the Map	
Save Your Structural Map	

Tool 2 – Checklist of Materials Needed for the workshop

How and Why: Use this checklist prior to the one day consultation to ensure that all of the necessary materials are on hand.

1 Flipchart Stand	
Flip Chart Size Paper	
200 Light Blue A4 Sheets (Barriers)	
200 Light Pink A4 Sheets (Options)	
A4 white paper – 100	
50 markers (mixtures of black, blue and green)	
5 red markers	
Posterboards (if you can't stick blu tack on the walls)	
Blu tack and/or White sticky tape	
Writing pens for all participants	
Small post-it notes (2 packs red)	
Red Sticky Dots (3 packs)	
Name tents for each participant	
Name badges for each participant	
Projector	
Connection to Projector	
Laptop	
Collective Intelligence ISM Software	

Tool 3 – Choosing a Training Venue

How and Why: Use this checklist to assist you in choosing a suitable training venue.

Location that is easily accessible to participants	
Large Room that can be reconfigured	
Large wall space for overhead projections	
Parallel large wall space for Barriers and Options	
Poster boards if it is not possible to stick barriers on the wall	
U-Shape set-up	
Natural Daylight	

Tool 4 – Event Debrief

How and Why: Use this worksheet to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of your consultation and transfer lessons to future consultations.

Strengths – What worked well?

Weaknesses – What didn't work so well?

Lessons Learned – What would I do differently the next time around?

APPENDICES

Appendix 1 – Interpretive Structural Modelling Software Guide

This Appendix details how to use the ISM software for the Sea2See consultations. All partners are advised to run a **test consultation** in-house prior to the actual consultation to ensure they are familiar with all aspects of the software. It is important to note that the main facilitator who will be running the consultation will NOT be in charge of entering the data into the software. The main facilitator will be focused on facilitating the participants through the Collective Intelligence Stages. A second co-facilitator will be tasked with this job. Both facilitators should however have a **good knowledge of the software**.

Opening the Software

When you first open the ISM software, you will see five tabs at the top of the screen. These are: workshop information, participants, barriers, voting and structuring. In order to move from one tab to another, simply click on the tab that you wish to go to.

Prior to the Consultation

A number of tasks can be completed prior to the consultation. Firstly, the **workshop information** may be entered into the tab. Here, you can enter the trigger question, context statement, title, date, host organization, location and objectives. Once this information is entered, you can save the document by clicking File and Save.

The second task which you can complete prior to the consultation is to enter the **participant's information**. In this step, you must enter information about each of the participants who are taking part in the consultation. You can enter information such as first name, last name, job title, address, type of participant (participant, observer or facilitator) and telephone number. After you input the information for the first participant click the “next” button rather than “save”. By clicking next, rather than save you are brought to the next line and can enter the next participants' information.

The most important pieces of information to include in this step are the **participant's names**, and whether they are a **participant, observer or facilitator**. This information will be required during the voting stage. If you need to delete a participant from the list, click on the selected participant from the list, and at the bottom right-hand side of the screen, click the button that says “Delete Selected Participants”. Once all of the participant information is inputted, save the file.

The final task which partners can complete prior to the consultation is to enter the necessary information in the **structuring tab**. In the keyword tab partners should enter the words, **“significantly aggravates”**. In the context statement partner should enter the word **“Does”**. As these words are entered into the software, they will appear on the screen which will be shown to partners during the structuring phase. Save the file once all of this information is inputted.

Generating Barriers

The first set of barriers will be entered into the software once the working group has collated and organized the barriers collected via the survey. As the facilitator will be able to read all of the barriers prior to entering them into the software, it is advised that **all duplicates be removed** prior to entering them into the software. If an idea is actually two barriers, the facilitator is advised to **split this barrier** statement into two separate and distinct barriers prior to entering it into the software.

The second set of barriers could be entered into the software after the stage of collective barrier generation during the first part of the workshop, following the same structure as above. As previously mentioned in relation to the participant information, press the **“new”** button rather than the **“save”** button after each idea is entered into the software.

Categorisation Stage

During the final phase of the categorisation stage, participants will be asked to vote for one idea from each category which they feel is the most important. They will then be given four additional votes which they can place on any idea which they feel is important. Based on this, the facilitators will identify the **top 12 barriers** that will be structured by the group. (12 is the ideal number to deal with during the next stages of the consultation process).

In order to move the barriers into the structuring tab, click on the individual idea and press the arrow button that faces right. The idea will then move to your **structuring set**. If you accidentally move a wrong idea to the structuring set click on it and press the arrow that points left and it will move out of the structuring set.

Structuring barriers Stage

Open the structuring tab on the software and select **“my structuring set”** from the Select Structuring Set Tab. Click on Toggle Fullscreen to ensure that participants can see the questions clearly. As the participants vote yes or no, click the relevant button. You may wish to show the participants the map as it progresses, if so click on the view graph button.

When all of the relational questions have been asked, show the participants the map and give them some time to digest the information. At this stage it might transpire that partners do feel the location of one or more barriers in the map do not portray the situation accurately. At this stage, partners can be given the option to take these barriers out of the map and to restructure them.

Restructuring Barriers

In order to restructure an idea you must return to the voting tab and the **“Structuring Sets”** section. Select the idea which the group wishes to restructure and click the arrow that faces left. The idea will be removed from your structuring set and hence then map. You then must move the idea back to the structuring set by clicking on it and clicking the arrow that faces right. Return to the structuring tab and the group will be asked **a second series of relational questions** relating to that particular barrier. Once all of these questions are answered the group will be presented with a new map.

Appendix 3 – Proposing Options Handout

1. Review the category
2. Think about the following Trigger Question:

What are the options for overcoming the barriers/challenges in this category (category title)?

3. Consider the following

- Initiatives
- Strategies
- Programmes
- Actions
- Recommendations
- Policies
- Practices
- Activities

4. Generate items using action verbs, such as:

Create
Establish
Set up
Promote

Demand
Plan
Develop
Conduct

Encourage
Build
Organize
Change

Appendix 4 – Overview of the Workshop

A suggested timeline can be seen below.

8.30 – 8.45	Participant Registration
9.00 – 10.00	Welcome and Overview of Goals Participants Introduce Themselves Provide an Overview of the Stages in the Workshop
10.00 – 10.20	Review of Categorisation and collective Barrier Generation (2nd stage)
10.20 – 10.50	Second Stage Barrier Categorisation with Participants
10.50 – 11.00	Review Final Categorisation and Voting for the most important barriers
11.00 – 11.15	Coffee Break (facilitators move selected barriers into the structuring field in the software)
11.15 – 13.00	Begin Barrier Structuring
13.00 – 14.00	Lunch Break
14.00 – 14.45	Continue Barrier Structuring
14.45 – 15.45	Generating Options
15.45 – 16.00	Coffee Break
16.00 – 17.30	Generating Options
17.30 – 17.45	Closure of Consultation Workshop and Follow-Up

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- ⁱ Ocean Network (2013) Available at:<http://www.coexploration.org/oceanliteracy/documents/OceanLitChart.pdf>
- ⁱⁱ Hastings, G. and Domegan, C. (2014) *Social Marketing From Tunes to Symphonies*, 2nd Edition, London: Routledge.
- ⁱⁱⁱ European Commission, Sea Change Description of Work.
- ^{iv} Hastings, G. and Domegan, C. (2014) *Social Marketing from Tunes to Symphonies*, 2nd Edition, London: Routledge.
- ^v Hastings, G. (2015) Public health and the value if disobedience. *Public Health*. Available online 29th May 2015 at doi:10.1016/j.puhe.2015.03.010
- ^{vi} Domegan, C. (2015) Sea Change WP2 SIPPs, Sea Change Kick-Off Meeting, 12th – 14th May 2015.
- ^{vii} <http://www.tepsie.eu/>
- ^{viii} Alexander G.C. 'Interactive Management: An emancipatory methodology' *Systemic Practice and Action Research* 15.2 (2002) 114
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Categories and barriers (OBJECTIVE: identify barriers to teaching 12-19 years old about the ocean.)

1) POLICY

- 1.1 Experiential education on this topic is not institutionally promoted.
- 1.2 There is a lack of a systemic approach to the system of teaching curricular competences.
- 1.3 Textbooks and classroom activities do not deal with these contents because of their complexity and lack of ready to use resources for teachers.

2) LACK OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THE OCEAN

- 2.1 The main problem of Environmental education around seas and oceans is that people live away from the sea. And even if they live in coastal areas, they do not see the importance of the ocean in their daily life.
- 2.2 The sea is considered as an unlimited and unalterable resource to be used. It is only superficially known, but its internal processes are unknown.
- 2.3 Insufficient knowledge of the marine environment, especially on the part of teachers to be able to develop school or classroom projects linked to the seas and oceans.

3) PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTIC OF THE MEAN

- 3.1 Difficulty in seeing what's in the water and knowing what's down there.
- 3.2 The sea can be dangerous. Not everybody can swim, not all of those who can swim do it well and the sea will always be seen as a place where you can drown. This is especially true for the teachers who carry out the activities.
- 3.3 The factor of seasonality and weather conditions can hamper the possibility of carrying out educational activities at sea all year round

4) SOCIETY MINDSET

- 4.1 Failure to appreciate the benefits that our individual actions can generate in the conservation of the marine environment.
- 4.2 Difficulty in establishing a link between our daily lives and the benefits that the sea provides or the impacts that our actions have on the sea.
- 4.3 Disregard or indifference towards issues with the label "environmental".

5) TEACHER DEVELOPMENT TRAINING

- 5.1 Lack of training opportunities for teachers regarding environmental and ocean issues,
- 5.2 Inability to teach this subject without the support of external actors (teachers do not feel confident enough to teach about the ocean)
- 5.3 Lack of quality educational projects and programmes (project-based) that provide access to knowledge about the oceans